

Conference Abstract

The situation of *Umbra krameri* Walbaum, 1792, in Romania

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Abstract

The European mudminnow (*Umbra krameri*) is an endemic species of the Danube and Dniester River basins and is classified as a vulnerable species on the IUCN Red List. Due to the drainage of marshes and swamps, as well as the significant reduction of floodplains, its populations in the Carpathian Basin have drastically declined in recent decades. In Romania, its distribution is restricted to wetland habitats at lower altitudes outside the Carpathians. During our surveys over the past 10 years, the species has not been found in many of its previously known locations. However, we have discovered several new, previously unknown populations (Suppl. material 1 (e.g., Homorodul Vechi River, Upper Ier Watershed etc.)). These populations do not indicate the species' expansion but rather highlight the under-researched nature of its potential habitats. Restoring the species' former habitats, along with the proper protection of its current habitats, could significantly improve the species' situation. At the same time, reassessing its current status and reclassify the species from the vulnerable category to the endangered category is necessary.

Presenting author

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: The situation of *Umbra krameri* Walbaum, 1792, in Romania

[doi](#)

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Data type: map

Brief description: *Umbra krameri* in Romania after 2015.

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